

AGENIUM SPACE

Benchmarking Deep Neural Networks on space compatible hardware for EO data extraction and reduction.

N.-M. Lemoine¹, F. de Vieilleville¹, A. Lagrange¹, M. Verm¹, N. Dublé¹, R. Camarero², B. Le Saux³

AGENIUM SPACE¹, ESTEC², ESRIN-PHILAB³

AI challenges participated:

SpotGeo 1st place!

<https://kelvins.esa.int/spot-the-geo-satellites/home/>

AIRQuality 2nd place!

<https://ai4eo.eu/ai4eo-challenge1>

Space Debris, the origin 4th place

<https://kelvins.esa.int/space-debris-the-origin/home/>

Cloud Cover Detection

Less than 1% gap with the winner

<https://www.drivendata.org/competitions/83/cloud-cover/leaderboard/>

Flight heritage:

UniBap ION

Forest detection onboard CPU

PLAN DE RELANCE SPATIAL

cnes

Why deep learning at the edge?

- Autonomous decision making
- Latency reduction
- Downlink cost reduction

However, is very complex due:

- Limited computation power
- Limited energy
- Limited memory capacities

Result of DEEP-CUBE project realised with the help of via ESA GSTP MAKE:

	Cloud Coverage (S2) RGB+NIR	Deforestation (S2) RGB+NIR	Boat Detection (HR) RGB	Snow VS Clouds RGB+NIR
Segmentation	✓	✓		✓
Detection			✓	

Showcase: measured cloud coverage over France using all Sentinel-2 captures between 01-2016 and 12-2021 (40552 acquisitions). Average 56% pixels are clouds.

All master models are around 90% F1-score (harmonic mean of precision and recall).

Simplification is measured as reduction in models' parameters and resulting attrition of the model.

	Cloud (S2) RGB+NIR	Deforestation (S2) RGB+NIR	Boat Detection (HR) RGB	Snow vs Clouds RGB+NIR
Reduction Factor	x60 59M → 1M	x80 24M → 300k	x80 24M → 300k	x120 59M → 500k
Attrition	≈6%	<3%	≈5%	<5%

	Xilinx Zynq 7000 SocFPGA → Z7045	Xilinx Zynq UltraScale+ SocFPGA → SDR Xiphos Q8, Leopard	Xilinx Kintex Ultrascale FPGA → KU060	Intel Movidius 2 VPU → Ubotica's CogniSat	AMD G-Series CPU/GPU → Unibap's iX5 on ION	Intel I7-9700K → reference
Segmentation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Detection	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Quantization	INT8	INT8	INT8	FP16	INT8/FP16/FP32	FP32/FP16
Space Qualification	Space qualified	Space qualified	Space qualified	Used in space	Use in space	X

No attrition between distilled models and quantized models in FP16

Negligible attrition between distilled models and quantized models in INT8

On board AI depends both of HW and SW capabilities:

Soc FPGA/FPGA:		CONS	PROS
VHDL/Verilog/HLS		Long to develop	Ad Hoc
VITIS AI (Xilinx HW)	✓	Black Box	Short to develop
CPU (AMD G series)		CONS	PROS
TensorFlow	✓	Too heavy library	Fast to develop, OSS
TensorFlowLite	✓	INT8 backend is super slow	FP16, Fast to develop, OSS
Pytorch		INT8 backend is super slow	Fast to develop, OSS
GPU (AMD G/R series)		CONS	PROS
TensorFlow		Does not work	OSS
TensorFlowLite	✓	C++ only backend	Short to develop, OSS
VPU (Myriad)		CONS	PROS
OpenVINO	✓	Black Box	Short to develop, Low power

Space power consumption constraints

Software versions used for testing: VITIS AI = 1.2, TFLite = 2.4.3, Pytorch = 1.4-1.7, OpenVino = 2020.3

Unit: Average/Max Watt, dpu config

	Xilinx Zynq 7000 Soc FPGA		Xilinx Zynq UltraScale+ Soc FPGA		Xilinx Kintex Ultrascale FPGA		Intel Movidius 2 VPU		AMD G-Series CPU/GPU		Intel I7-9700K	
	avg/max [W]	dpu config	avg/max [W]	dpu config	avg/max [W]	dpu config	avg/max [W]	x	avg/max [W]	x	avg/max [W]	x
Segmentation (0.1M ~ 1M)	3.25 /5	1xB1152	10/15 /9/13	3xB4096 /2xB4096	3.324/3.324	1xB4096	1/1	---	≈10/≈10	---	95/95	---
Detection (0.3M ~ 1M)	3.25 /5	1xB1152	10/15 /9/13	3xB4096 /2xB4096	3.324/3.324	1xB4096	1/1	---	≈10/≈10	---	95/95	---

From our experiments, what are the best devices for DL in space ?

	Intel CPU Core i7-9700k (95W) [Pixels/W/s]	Xilinx Zynq 7000 (3,25W) [Pixels/W/s]	Xilinx Zynq Ultrascale+ (ZU+) (≈10W) [Pixels/W/s]	Xilinx Kintex Ultrascale FPGA [Pixels/W/s]	Intel myriad VPU 2 (1W) [Pixels/W/s]	AMD G-Series (iX5) (10W) [Pixels/W/s]
Cloud Segmentation	19k	68k	176k	<1k	172k	8k
Forest Segmentation (Deforestation)	32k	112k	212k	<1k	317k	19k
Snow VS Cloud Segmentation	21k	77k	185k	<1k	209k	9k
Boat Detection	108k	192k	601k	3k	641k	17k

90k px/W/s = 1 image 300x300/w/s

VPU and SoCs FPGA are good choices!
Still room for improvement on SoC FPGA SW!

input

output

- clouds
- background
- forest

Flight demonstration on ION satellite of a simplified forest segmentation algorithm (92% F1 score) using CPU on Unibap's iX5 : AMD G-series @10W

Future flights:

currently in orbit validation/demonstration phase

ESA OPS_SAT

Building our own VHDL IP:

Binary Models

Device Agnostic

Upgrade performances:

Search for more efficient architectures

Better efficiency of our model with latest version of VAI

QUESTIONS?

Address:

1, avenue de l'Europe
31400 TOULOUSE
FRANCE

Contacts:

Sales: sales.space@agenium.com

Sales phone: +33-646786334

Author: nicolas-marcel.lemoine@agenium.com

